

EXPLORING THE PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS TOWARDS STUDENT POLITICAL ORGANIZATION AT BUIITEMS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15516076>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
02 April, 2025	02 May, 2025	17 May, 2025	26 May, 2025

ABSTRACT

Student unions play an important role in the development of peaceful democratic political culture in any state. Since in Pakistan student unions were banned and as a result student political organizations were emerged. These student political organizations are important component of the political parties. Much has been written on the role of political organizations; however, very less academic work has been done on the perception of students towards political organization in higher education institutions of Baluchistan. Therefore, this study sought to examine the perception of students towards political organizations in BUIITEMS. This study has used mixed method design, in order to explore that how student perceive student political organizations at BUIITEMS and the factors that influence their perceptions. Student of 6th and 8th semester of Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities (FSSH) were selected by purposive sampling. Quantitative questionnaires were analysed and summarized through descriptive analysis using SPSS. While Qualitative semi-structure interviews were analysed through thematic analysis. This study found that students were pessimistic about the role of political organizations in BUIITEMS. The factor that contributed in this pessimism was that these organizations were untrustworthy and political motivated

Keywords: Student politicizes, organizations, Perception, Higher Institutions, BUIITEMS

INTRODUCTION

Politics is defined by Giddens and Sutton (2017), “politics refers to power which is used to affect the scope and control of governmental activities”. It keeps check and balance by opposing and pressurizing Government’s policies which are against the interest of the majority of the masses. Heywood, Miller and Laski defined it as “Politics is uniquely and distinctly connected with the activities of the state”. This connection with the activities of the state in democratic states make the government to have their concern in the policies. Policies which do not address and fulfill the need of the people are opposed by the political parties, as people’s representatives.

In Pakistan Student political organizations work from the grass root level, starting from secondary education than in the higher education institutions, same as political parties do on national level. These organizations dress the students’ concerns and oppose the institutions’ and government policies which are not beneficial for students. In contrast to the Students unions which are not binding to any political party, student political organization work through a specific organized pattern under its mother political party. Students unions are banned by the Supreme Court of Pakistan in July, 1992 (Khan & Zaman, 2020). Student political organizations have been on the front page for the students

interests. They are active all over Pakistan in the basis of their mother party's Manifesto. Historically, these organization has led several movements against injustice and atrocities by the state and other authorities, particularly in the higher education institutions. For example, in East Pakistan, Dhaka University student led the movement against state for the discrimination of Bengali language. In West Pakistan, movement led by students against the 3 year degree program and topple the Ayub Khan regime (Qadir et al., n.d.)

Student political organizations has been active in Baluchistan for a long time but less work is conducted to highlight their role in the education institutions. Student politics is active in several education institutions in Baluchistan and has influenced students. This study intended to explore the student perception towards student political organizations in higher education institutions particularly, at BUIITEMS, Quetta. As very less study has conducted on the role of student political organizations in the institutions so the findings of this research will contribute by exploring the perception of students regarding the student political organizations at Balochsitan University of Information, Technology and Management Sciences (BUIITEMS).

1.1 Problem Statement

In the third world countries the student politics is active in the higher education institutions and has contributed in both campus politics and has also influenced state policies. The student politics has often been taken negative act by the society, students and by university administrations (Altbach, 1984). Currently student's unions are banned in Pakistan and students' organizations came into existence (Qadir et al., n.d.). Student politics and students' organizations got very less literature in Baluchistan and limited study has been conducted on the perception of students. The majority of the work that has already been written has focused on the function and role of student political organizations, rarely addressing how students see these organizations. We found that the "perception of students towards student political organizations" is a crucial issue that has to be addressed in higher education, particularly in BUIITEMS, Quetta. This study seeks to fill the gap by examining the perception of students towards student political organizations in

Baluchistan University of Information, Technology and Management Sciences.

1.2 Research Questions

Q.NO 1. How do student perceive political organizations in BUIITEMS?

Q.NO 2. What factors influence the perception of students towards political organizations?

1.3 Research Objectives

To analyze student's perception towards political organizations at BUIITEMS.

To explore the motivational driver that shape the perception of students towards political organization at BUIITEMS.

1.5 Research Design

The research conducted to analyze the perception of students towards political organization and the factor that influence student for the participation and abstention in these organizations. The purpose of research was to explore the perception of students towards political organization at BUIITEMS. This study required mixed method research approach in which both quantitative and qualitative data was collected. The gap of the research was analyzed by implementing quantitative and qualitative research questions.

Qualitative data methods involves collecting data through interviews, and focused group discussion. This study requires primary data collection from students of BUIITEMS. The population of BUIITEMS was selected through purposive sampling to specify the students of 6th semester and 8th semester of Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities (FSSH).

This study required thematic analysis in which 12 interviews were conducted from students of FSSH at BUIITEMS. After data collection through semi-structure interviews, thematic analysis applied to analyze the data.

The quantitative research involves several analyses which includes descriptive stats and inferential stats. The data was collected from students of 6th and 8th semester of Faculty of Social sciences and Humanities at BUIITEMS through Morgan and Krejcie table of sampling. According to Morgan and Krejcie table of sampling, if the population size is 500, then the sample size will be 217. The collection of quantitative data required 217 surveys which was analyzed by descriptive stats.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Politics is defined by Giddens and Sutton (2017), "politics refers to power which is used to affect the scope and control of governmental activities". It keeps check and balance by opposing and pressurizing Government's policies which are against the interest of the majority of the masses. Heywood, Miller and Laski defined it as "Politics is uniquely and distinctly connected with the activities of the state". This connection with the activities of the state in democratic states make the government to have their concern in the policies. Policies which do not address and fulfill the need of the people are opposed by the political parties, as people's representatives.

Furthermore, Giddens and Sutton (2017) also noted that "when students collectively play a significant role in politics by leveraging their united power to influence governmental actions, this is recognized as student politics. Student politics may be seen as a form of socialization that prepares students to fulfill their civic duties, defend their rights, and challenge the authorities for their unfair actions. Depending on a country's nature and structure, various forms of student politics have been identified by different scholars (Heywood, 1997; Altbach, 1974; Ottaway, 1968). Among the different categories, two types of student politics—Student Union and Party-backed Student Politics—are particularly common worldwide (Nasrin & Rahman, 2019).

A student union is an association of the majority of students at an institution to which this part applies, whose principal purposes include promoting the general interests of its members as students," states Section 20 of the UK Education Act of 1994 (Tareq, 2017). While, most nations have several national political parties, with the exception of a few totalitarian regimes (Heywood, 1997). These national parties often have connected, partnered, or linked wings within various professional groupings. In these situations, student unions transform into politically charged organizations that support the growth of future leaders. There are several examples where student politics operate inside universities with the direct supervision of major political parties (Khaleduzzaman, 2014; Alam et al., 2011; Ullah, 2001).

Predominantly, Student politics has a long history, it was started in 1848 with German

nationalism. Throughout 1930s and 1940s they supported Hitler in Germany and Mussolini in Italy when both leaders were in power. The emergence of Indonesian nationalism and the creation of a national language were also greatly influenced by students. They took an active part in the successful independence-promoting anti-colonial campaigns. The Latin American Reform Movement of 1918, which started in Argentina and spread across the continent, included students in governance and societal processes. Student unions were notably active in the 1960s in the United States and achieved significant success (Altbach, 1989). However, before the subcontinent was divided, Pakistan had a long and rich history of student politics, which may be divided into two phases: the first, which lasted from 1857 to 1937, and the second, which lasted from 1937 to 1947 (Qadir et al., n.d.).

In Pakistan Student political organizations work from the grass root level, starting from secondary education than in the higher education institutions, same as political parties do on national level. These organizations dress the students' concerns and oppose the institutions' and government policies which are not beneficial for students. In contrast to the Students unions which are not binding to any political party, student political organization work through a specific organized pattern under its mother political party. Students unions are banned by the Supreme Court of Pakistan in July, 1992 (Khan & Zaman, 2020). Student political organizations have been on the front page for the students interests. They are active all over Pakistan in the basis of their mother party's Manifesto. Historically, these organization has led several movements against injustice and atrocities by the state and other authorities, particularly in the higher education institutions. For example, in East Pakistan, Dhaka University student led the movement against state for the discrimination of Bengali language. In West Pakistan, movement led by students against the 3 year degree program and topple the Ayub Khan regime (Qadir et al., n.d.).

After the independence, in 1947, the only established student organization was the Muslim Student Federation (MFS). The Islamic Jamiat-e-Talaba (IJT) was founded in Lahore in December 1947, and the Democratic Students' Federation in 1948. Additional student organizations that

have developed over time include the Peoples Students Federation (PSF), All Pakistan Mohajir Students Organization (APMSO), Baloch Students Organization (BSO), Pakhtun Students Federation (PkSF), Anjuman Talaba-e-Islam (ATI), Imamia Students Organization (ISO), Punjabi Students Federation, Jiye Sindh Federation, and National Students Federation (NSF) (Qadir et al., n.d.).

The first organized student movement in Pakistan was in favor of Bengali language, with the significant contribution from the students of Dhaka University. In Sindh, students protested against the separation of Karachi from Sindh. While in 1952, Punjabi students also protested against the report of the Basic Principles Committee and played a role in the Khatam-i-Nabuwat Movement (1948-1953). Furthermore, student protested against Ayub Khan's education policy (1961-62) of three-year degree program. Students also played key role in the political movement against the Tashkent Declaration (1966), which contributed significantly to President Ayub Khan's downfall in 1969 (Qadir et al., n.d.).

The collapse of Ayub Khan Regime was followed by the secession of East Pakistan and the creation of Bangladesh. In west Pakistan, the Pakistan People's Party (PPP) was voted to power on 1970 and many labor and student organizations were instrumental in anti-Ayub campaign (Javid, 2019). Moreover, Bhutto's government in 1977 integrated student unions into the university governance structure, making several significant decisions, student union representatives were given membership in the university syndicate, they become members of the university senate, they joined the academic council, and they became members of the disciplinary committee (Qadir et al., n.d.).

However, martial law dictator Zia-ul-Haq imposed restriction on student unions in 1984. Pakistan student politics were once again altered by General Zia-ul-Haq's 1977 overthrow of the country's first PPP administration. Zia's regime enjoyed the support of right-wing parties and student organizations that had supported the Pakistan National Alliance (PNA) and were aligned with the IJT and MSF (Javid, 2019). In the following years, increasing repression by the Zia regime and violent on-campus activities by the IJT led to more frequent armed clashes between

rival student groups. This situation was exacerbated by the influx of weapons from the Afghan war, which, when wielded by student unions, led to unprecedented levels of death and injury. These factors—the persistence of anti-regime student groups and the weaponization of student politics—provided the pretext for General Zia-ul-Haq's ban on student politics in 1984 (Butt, 2009; Paracha, 2009).

When democracy was reinstated in 1988, Prime Minister Benazir Bhutto made the decision to remove the prohibition on student unions in academic settings (Qadir et al., n.d.). For the rest of the 1990s, student politics remained largely informal; while IJT managed to reassert itself on campuses throughout the country, groups like the MSF and PSF continued to operate but with diminishing influence and support. However, by the time Pakistan experienced its third military coup in 1999, bringing General Pervez Musharraf to power, the student politics of previous decades had mostly ended (Javid, 2019).

While the IJT maintained a presence in universities and colleges, particularly in Punjab, but increasingly focused on regulating students on campus rather than engaging in mainstream politics. According to Paracha (2009) and Nelson (2011), this apathy could be explained by two significant factors. First, a generation of students who had grown up under the shadow of General Zia-ul-Haq's prohibitions on student politics coincided with the establishment of the Musharraf dictatorship. This effect was compounded by the widespread belief that student politics in the 1980s and 1990s had been reduced to violent clashes between unsavory elements acting as extensions of national-level political parties. Second, the decline of student politics created space for alternative organizations, such as more radical national and transnational Islamist groups tolerated and even nurtured by the state, to attract politically interested students.

Thus, it came as a surprise when students from prestigious private universities like the Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS), Beacon House National University (BNU), and the National University of Computer and Emerging Sciences (commonly known as FAST) participated in the anti-Musharraf movement of 2007—a movement that was sparked by a judicial crisis that followed Musharraf's arbitrary and

unlawful dismissal of the nation's Chief Justice (Javid, 2019). As argued by Bolognani (2011), Talib (2011), and Kalra (2018), the participation of students from universities like LUMS in anti-Musharraf movement was driven by a combination of factors. These students, possessing relatively high levels of privilege. They also benefited from the presence of faculty and peers committed to raising authoritarian rule. Moreover, the media landscape in Pakistan and globally facilitated their protest activities.

In parallel, Imran Khan, the leader of PTI, established the Insaf Student Federation (ISF) on November 14, 2007, following a confrontation with IJT activities at Punjab University. This move was aimed at mobilizing students against the Musharraf regime and garnering support for PTI's political ambitions. Furthermore, following election that followed the overthrow of Musharraf dictatorship in 2008, Prime Minister Yousaf Raza Gillani of PP pledged to lift the long standing prohibition on student organizations. However, neither the PPP nor the PML-N government that succeeded it in 2013 took action in this regard. Therefore, student politics are still prohibited in Pakistan, notwithstanding a resolution issued by the senate in 2017 advocating for the resuscitation of student unions (Javid, 2019).

Student politics in Higher Education played a crucial role while producing leaderships. Professional political leaders such as Mr. Javid Hashmi, Mr. Liaqat Baloch, Mr. Jahangir Badr, Mr. Ahsan Iqbal, Mr. Ghulam Abbas, and Mr. Altaf Hussain—founder of the APMSO and leader of the MQM—as well as Dr. Abdul Hayee Baloch, President of National Party—have all emerged from Pakistani educational institutions (Qadir et al., n.d.). Moreover, Mathew Nelson (2011) suggests that viewing student politics in Pakistan through the lens of national, territorial, ideological, sectarian, and ethnic divisions obscures how, since the 1990s, the decline of traditional student unions has led many young people to join and support transnational organizations, primarily Islamist in nature, which offer a political vision transcending the largely static politics of local organizations (Nelson, 2011).

Present-day student organization connected to major political parties are essentially ideological and electoral pawns of their parent organizations.

Their ability to discuss more significant political concerns in Pakistan now is restricted by this alliance. Given this background, it is critical to investigate how students who organize outside of these restrictions function in a setting where official political activity is prohibited, student organization participation is restricted, and state policies persistently stifle movements that support social and economic justice, the rights of minorities, and provincial autonomy. This problem is especially acute for the left-Wing organizations, which are still trying to recover after decades of the official hostility and the near-complete disappearance of classic Left-wing groups like the DSF and PSF from mainstream politics. The progressive Labor Wing (PLW), the Insaf Students Federation (ISF), and the Democratic Students Alliance (DSA) are the subjects of the case studies that follow. These studies show how the demands of electoral competition, the allure of populist mobilization, and the desire for Radical change combine to shape various paths of student political participation in a Pakistan that is becoming more democratic (Javid, 2019).

Theoretical Framework

This study applies the theory of social identity (SIT) developed by Tajfel and Turner (1979) to study student perceptions towards student political organizations. Social Identity Theory suggests that people are ranked in social groups, which significantly affects one's attitudes, behaviors and sense of belonging. The theory highlights three important processes: Social classification, Social identification, and social comparison.

Student political organizations act as potential social groups, allowing students to adjust based on shared ideology, affiliation, or group identity. However, research results shows that most students are against student political organizations. This can be explained by a negative social comparison, when students perceive political groups as divided, destructive or displaced with their academic and social priorities. Furthermore, students who are not associated with political groups can consider themselves as part of the student's larger apolitical identity, and can strengthen their opposition to such organizations. A negative perception of student organizations can be

related to negative stereotypes, past experiences, or social narratives that position political participation as counterproductive in relation to academic success.

By the lens of Social Identity Theory, this study highlights how group dynamics, identity formation, and intergroup perceptions influence student's stance on political organizations. The resistance towards student politics suggests that students may prioritize an academic or professional identity over a political one, leading

to a collective disassociation from student political groups at BUITEMS.

RESULTS

4.1 Quantitative Results

Quantitative results was investigated from the response to the survey used for this study. This data was analyzed through descriptive analysis using SPSS. Quantitative results contained only one variable called perception. The analysis yielded the following outcomes.

Table NO 4.1.2

How do you perceive the influence of political organizations on academic activities within the social sciences faculty?

	f	%
no influence	53	24.4
minor influence	62	28.6
moderate influence	54	24.9
significant influence	37	17.1
very significant influence	11	5.1

24.4% of the respondents perceive no influence of political organizations on academic activities within the social sciences faculty. They do not have affiliation with political organizations which lead them to an out-group discrimination. 28.6% of the respondents perceive minor influence of political organizations on academic activities within the social sciences faculty. They do not identify themselves as part of the organizations but they do slightly favor them which means they have affiliation with them. 22.2% of the respondents perceives very much influence of

political organizations on academic activities within the social sciences faculty. They identify themselves as being part of the political organizations which lead them to an in-group favor in comparison with others. The remaining 24.9% of the respondents perceive moderate influence of political organizations on academic activities within the social sciences faculty. They do not identify themselves as being part of the political organization but do possess affiliation with them which is why he favors their role moderately.

Figure 4.1.2

The Influence of Political Organizations on academic activities within the Social Sciences Faculty.

Figure 4.1.2

Figure 4.1.2 shows the influence of political organizations on academic activities within the

social sciences faculty. 24.42% responded to no influence, 28.57% responded to minor influence, 24.88% responded to moderate

influence, 17.05% responded significant influence and 5.07% responded to very significant influence.

Table NO 4.1.3

Questions	SA		A		N		D		SD	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Do you perceive the presence of political organizations positively contribute to campus life at BUITEMS?	24	11.1	56	25.8	63	29.0	43	19.8	31	14.3
In your opinion, do political organizations at BUITEMS create an atmosphere conducive to healthy debates and discussions?	38	17.5	59	27.2	66	30.4	42	19.4	12	5.5

Note: SA = strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree.

36.9% of the respondents perceive that the presence of political organizations contribute positively to the campus life at BUITEMS. The concepts of Social identification and Social comparison in Social Identity Theory explains it as those who identify their group would then do favor it in comparison of others. Those respondents who perceives the presence of political organizations contribute positively to the campus life at BUITEMS are themselves affiliated with it, according to the above theory. While 34.1% of the respondents do not perceive the presence of political organizations contribution positively to the campus life at BUITEMS. This include those students who are not affiliated with any organization who possess negative perception against political organizations. The remaining 29% of the respondents remained neutral regarding the political organizations positive contribution to campus life at BUITEMS. The neutral responses might indicate students who do not strongly identify with or have limited engagement with any political organizations. Their neutral stance could reflect a lack of strong

in-group or out-group affiliation influencing their perception.

44.7% of the respondents possess the opinion that political organizations at BUITEMS do create an atmosphere conducive to healthy debates and discussions. They have this opinion in favor of political organizations because they have some kind of affiliation with them, as the theory argue that the person will favor his group over others. While 24.9% of the respondents have the opinion that political organizations at BUITEMS do not create an atmosphere conducive to healthy debates and discussions. They are not part of political organizations and have no affiliations with them which lead their opinion against these organizations, as the theory argue that a person would do out-group discrimination. The remaining 30.4% of the respondents remained neutral regarding the creation of conducive atmosphere to healthy debates and discussions by political organizations at BUITEMS. The neutral responses might indicate students who do not strongly identify with or have limited engagement with any political organizations. Their neutral stance could reflect a lack of strong in-group or out-group affiliation influencing their perception.

Figure 4.1.3

Perception of students towards the presence of Political Organizations positive contribution to campus life at BUITEMS.

Figure 4.1.3

Figure 4.1.3 shows the perception of the students towards the presence of political organization positive contribution to campus life at

BUITEMS. 11.06% responded to strongly agree, 25.81% responded to agree, 29.03% responded to neutral, 19.82% responded to disagree and 14.29% responded to strongly disagree.

Figure 4.1.4

Political Organizations at BUITEMS create an atmosphere conducive to healthy debates and discussion.

Figure 4.1.4

Figure 4.1.4 shows the political organizations at BUITEMS create an atmosphere conducive to healthy debates and discussions. 17.51%

responded to strongly agree, 27.19% responded to agree, 30.41% responded to neutral, 19.35% responded to disagree and 5.53% responded to strongly disagree.

Table NO 4.1.5

Questions	NAA		S		M		VM		E	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
To what extent do you believe political organizations positively contribute to the academic environment at BUITEMS?	59	27.2	68	31.3	56	25.8	25	11.5	9	4.1

To what extent do you feel comfortable expressing your political views or affiliations on campus? 72 33.2 71 32.7 45 20.7 21 9.7 8 3.7

Note: NAA=not at all, S=slightly, M=moderately, VM=very much, E=extremely.

27.2% do not believe political organizations positively contribute to the academic environment at BUITEMS. They do not have affiliation with any of the organization which lead them to an out-group discrimination. 31.3% slightly believe political organizations positively contribute to the academic environment at BUITEMS. They are, to some extent, affiliated with political organization or their parent party which lead them to a slight favor. 15.6% do believe political organizations positively contribute to the academic environment at BUITEMS. They are affiliated with political organizations which lead them to in-group favoritism in comparison of others, which theory argues. While 25.8% moderately believe political organizations positively contribute to the academic environment at BUITEMS. They do not identify themselves part of the political organizations but have affiliation with them.

33.2% do not feel comfortable expressing their views or political affiliations on campus. They do not identify themselves as part of the political organizations due to which they do not feel comfortable expressing their views. 32.7% slightly feel comfortable expressing their views or political affiliations on campus. They also do not freely identify themselves part of the political organizations but can express their views in their friend circle or class which is limited. 11.4% do feel comfortable expressing their views or political affiliations on campus. They identify themselves as being part of the political organization which lead them to express their views comfortably either in favor or against any organization. While 20.7% moderately feel comfortable expressing their views or political affiliations on campus. They do not identify themselves as being part of any political organization but do possess affiliation with them.

Figure 4.1.5

Political Organizations positively contribute to the academic environment at BUITEMS to a significant extend.

Figure 4.1.5

Figure 4.1.5 shows political organizations positively contribute to the academic environment at BUITEMS to a significant extent.

27.19% responded to not at all, 31.34% responded to slightly, 25.81% responded to moderately, 11.52% responded to very much and 4.15% responded to extremely.

Figure 4.1.6
 Feeling comfortable by expressing political views or affiliation on campus.

Figure 4.1.6

Figure 4.1.6 shows feeling comfortable by expressing political views or affiliations on campus. 33.18% responded to not at all, 32.72% responded to slightly, 20.74% responded to moderately, 9.88% responded to very much and 3.69% responded to extremely.

4.2 Qualitative Results

A semi-structure interviews were conducted from students of Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities at BUISTEMS. The researcher used thematic analysis for the qualitative results. This qualitative data were analyzed through thematic analysis. The audiotaped data was first transcribed and then coded to arrive at major themes. The analysis yielded the following themes.

4.2.1 General perception of students

Student organizations are active in BUISTEMS and are playing great role inside campus. The theme General perception includes role and impact of student organizations and suggestions for improvement of student organizations. Student organizations play both positive and negative role. Most of the students perceive their role positively. They play a significant role in university environment by promoting and protecting students' rights inside campus. They resolve student issues which includes rising tuition fees, buses timing and non-availability etc. One of the respondents expressed his thoughts:

I think student organizations are must in every university campus. Student grievances and problems are resolved through them. They works for the Student Rights. It works as a catalyst for positive change.

Some of the students perceive their role negatively. Student organizations in BUISTEMS are divided on the basis of political parties, which are mostly nationalist parties, and divide students on ethnic basis. Political parties leads them to promote their political interests rather than being united for students interests which creates anarchic situation inside campus and they fight against each other. A respondent argued that: Student organizations play both positive and negative role. Politics aims to help others instead of fighting and having bad behavior towards each other and towards faculty and administration as well.

Student organizations have both positive and negative impact. Some of the students perceive they have positive impacts on students which includes addition to their political awareness and dealing with different people in different situations. One of the respondent advocated that: They do impact on the student body. For instance, once our scholarship was not accepted by the administration we were very upset for our scholarships then we went to student organizations to restore our scholarship in result they struggled for our genuine cause and restored the scholarships. These student organizations have positive impact on the students.

While most of the students perceive they have negative impacts on students and campus life. Student's behavior are changed after becoming part of any political organization and feel superior. Students tilt towards offensiveness as they are protected by their respective organization. An interviewee responded that:

They have negative impact on students, they always show their power and degrade weak students with their power and powerful students have control over these organizations.

Student organizations should support majority's cause instead of their own minority's cause (based on Political affiliation). They manipulates new comers/students who then take actions that are inappropriate which ruins their study and future. They should provide stable environment to female students who are interested to join them. Student organizations at BUITEMS, should work for non-member student rights and have positive impact on them. One of the respondents argued that:

Student organizations behavior towards students or female should be positive and good. Secondly, they should resolve the problem of students in positive way it should make good perceptions about student organization.

Student Organizations should become unite for students' interests. Do not be divided based on caste, ethnicity and sect, make a student union collectively, named as student union which would erase the differences among students. Student union should be led by an intellect student with mature and quality cabinet and include female students in union. One of the interviewee advocated for single student union and said:

I would say all the organizations should become unite for students own interests. Do not be divided based on caste, ethnicity and sect. Make a student union collectively. And make proper manifesto for collective gains. Deal them as intellect person.

4.2.2 Experience with Student political Organizations (Proponents and Critics)

Student organizations are active in BUITEMS and all of the students have experience with them in various ways. Experience with student political organizations theme includes personal experience, engagement/participation,

observation, and barriers that students are experiencing.

Most of the students do not have personal experience or affiliation with student organizations but are still effected by their policies and moves. Some students have suffered due to their strike while most of the female students are effected. One of respondent shared his experience in the following words:

I have personal experience. Once the organization did strike against the administration and main gates were closed by the student organization this act impact my perception negatively because when they closed the gate students suffered particularly female students

Most of the students in BUITEMS are not engaged or have not participated in any organization inside campus. The major reason behind it is the mother political parties of the organizations who influence the student politics for their own interests to propagate their manifesto which would incentivize students for their upcoming political career towards themselves. Students are willing to join student organizations but they avoid politics (influenced by political parties). A female respondent said that:

I have not thought to join it because I cannot resist there due to male dominance and political influence. They will not consider me to listen (or any other female student). I thought we should make our own student union with a manifesto that fulfills student needs and interests without any external (political) pressure.

Students have observed the positive role of organizations as well as their negative role on various occasions. They do influence university's policy and have played a vital role for the protection of faculty's rights. These organizations were part of the protest that was announced by the faculty against the administration for not paying their salaries and excluding house requisition which assisted faculty and were successful in creating a faculty union named as BUITEMS Staff Association (BSA).

Students faces many barriers regarding student organizations. First of all, an affidavit is signed by students by university administration in which a student would have to take oath for not joining any student organization otherwise he/she would be expelled from university. Then comes male dominance in every student organization which

creates a barrier for females to join and led the organization. One of the female interviewee said that:

As a female, I would say gender is a barrier. It is not tolerated to have female ruler. Secondly, there is a discourse in our society that female do not know about politics.

Students are restricted by family regarding joining of organizations which is a prime barrier. Most of the students are not joining them because they think it would ruin their studies and career. They are compelled to join meeting or attend rally/protest during their class time which lead them to not participate in any organization. Some students are not joining these organizations because they are divided on ethnic basis due to their nationalist mother political parties which has been divided students rather than uniting them. A student argued that:

There are a lot of barriers like family pressure, social barriers, ethnic divisions and they do not know how to deal students. There is lack of potential leadership in organization.

4.2.3 Trustworthiness of Student Political Organizations

Student organizations in BUIITEMS are active and do what they can do to achieve their personal interests or to advocate for student rights protection. But most of the people criticize them over their activities and that they cannot be trusted. It is because they mostly resolve issues of the students who are their organization's members. Some of the critiques blame them for the anarchic situation inside the campus through which they show their active presence and maximize their power. They are not trustworthy because they propagate their mother party's policy which may sometime contradict with students' interests. One of the respondent criticizes and said that:

The organizations which exist here in BUIITEMS are not aware of their own manifesto. They don't know what to do. They just showoff, to show others their activeness. They don't practice according to their manifesto, which creates distrust. I will not trust them and I am aware about what exactly they are doing in these organizations.

Some of the student thinks that they are trustworthy because they solely work for students' interests. Those students who advocated for their

trustworthiness were mostly their members or have been their members. One student argued that:

In my point of view, these student organizations are trust worthy only in one situation where they work under one umbrella together.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to explore the perception of students towards student political organizations in BUIITEMS. This chapter presents the findings of research questions, limitation, recommendations, suggestions for future research and conclusion. Based on analysis of data collected in this study, the researcher offers the following research questions.

RQ1: How do Students Perceive Student Political Organizations at BUIITEMS?

For the first quantitative research question regarding how do students perceive student political organizations in BUIITEMS, the data was gathered through survey of Likert-scale questionnaire, and used descriptive statistics to summarize and interpret the responses. The researcher found that the students of faculty of social sciences and humanities had negative perception towards student political organizations. The respondents in the surveys showed that most of student don't believe that political organizations positively contribute to the academic environment at BUIITEMS while some students were not even comfortable by expressing their political views or affiliations regarding student political organizations on campus. The participants showed that the student political organizations don't create an atmosphere conducive to healthy debates, discussions and positively contributions to campus life, therefore most of the students were not in favor of student political organizations and their activities at BUIITEMS.

RQ2: What Factors influence the student Perception towards Student Political Organizations?

For the second qualitative research question regarding what factors influence the student perception towards student political organizations, the data was gathered using semi-structure interviews, and used thematic analysis to interpret the data. After analyzing the data,

there were several factors which has influenced student's perception towards student political organizations. Since they face several challenges on a daily basis, students at BUIITEMS have an unfavorable opinion towards student organizations. The majority of students had personal experience with the organizations, which negatively affected the perceptions. Considering the functions of organizations, students don't consider them beneficial because all organizations are fulfilling the interest of their mother parties. Due to their weak performance, female participations are very less and alienated themselves from student politics because they had personal experience with the immature members of these organizations, therefore they don't feel comfortable and protected. Student politics are divided on the base of ethnicity rather than working under one umbrella which discourages other students for participating. Student unions are the only factor that student want to take part more than student political organizations which runs on their mother political manifesto. Furthermore, student political organizations disturb the academic activities of the participant in which they call for protest and gathering on any time and the member of organizations have to go come what may. In result, those student who are more interested in their studies rather than political activities becomes against the student organizations. Most of time, student perception effects due to intra-conflicts among student organizations which creates a negative image and student becomes against it. Regarding trustworthiness, most of students don't trust because of their illegal activities and immaturity of organization members. Student believes that the members of organizations are not well known about politics and student's genuine cause which becomes very difficult for other students to trust. Overall, due to several factors student's perceptions have been affected negatively towards student political organizations at BUIITEMS.

The mixed-method data collection indicated a pattern between the quantitative and qualitative findings, supporting the hypothesis. The results shows that student's perceptions towards student political organizations were generally unfavorable. While the quantitative responses confirmed the quantitative analysis statistically significant trend of dislike, they also participated

in interviews and offered deep insights into the causes underlying the perceptions. The hypothesis that students generally associated these organizations with negative actions or impacts is supported by the results, which showed distinct patterns and correlations between the responses.

Recommendations

The study explored the perception of students towards student political organizations at BUIITEMS. The findings revealed that majority of students have negative perception towards student political organizations.

In the light of research findings, it is recommended that student political organizations consider their activities and role in BUIITEMS. The following specific recommendations are provided:

1. Collective Efforts of Student Organizations:

Student organizations should act collectively, Instead of fighting and quarrelling to each other, which gives the impressions that student organizations are bad and produce negative perception of students towards student organizations.

2. Female Participations:

For student organizations to build positive perception, female participation is essential. Most of the time, female have a desire to participate in student organization. Because of the male dominance, female distance themselves and are unable to participate.

3. Recruitment:

Student organizations need to recruit politically matured students which produces smooth performance of organizations and the members becomes well known about their role and duty for the student issues and problems in institutions.

Suggestions for further Research

To further understand the perception of students towards student political organizations, future researcher should do research on union-based student politics in higher education institutions in Baluchistan, Quetta. Moreover, future researchers should also study the participation of female in student political organizations,

particularly in higher education institutions in Balochistan.

Balochistan has been the hub of student politics, particularly in the higher education institutions where students have been actively participate. Further research is also needed to understand the difference between student political organizations which are align with their mother parties and the student Unions which functions without the influence of any external actor where all student of different ethnic and cast participate in unions. Furthermore, future researcher could study the impact of student organizations on the academic activities of student and challenges they face while participating in the student political organizations.

Conclusion

Historically, student politics have been active in higher education institutions. This research aimed to explore the perception of students towards student political organizations at BUIITEMS. The study was based on quantitative and qualitative analysis of student perception and factors that influence student perception. The results indicate that most of student suffer and faced several challenges by these organization which made their perception negative towards student political organizations at BUIITEMS. However, this study contained some unpredicted results which were not in line with the hypotheses. There was trend in results that the participation of female and the function of all student political organizations in one umbrella were not in line with the hypotheses.

This research has shown that the perception of student at BUIITEMS have been pursued as a negative act. However, some student showed that the organizations has played vital role, raising voice for admission fees, scholarships, and other genuine issues of student. Student political organization have played some of crucial role in solving the student problems where these organizations make their image clear and student perceive them positively at BUIITEMS. Due to the limitation of the current study, further research is needed on the student political organization in which student of other universities of Balochistan and their perception as well as the participation of female.

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